

A phenomenological study of administrative issues and challenges faced by secondary school headmasters in district Lasbela

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ABSTRACT: Using a phenomenological approach, this study explores secondary school headmasters' perspectives of administrative issues in District Lasbela, Balochistan. The study's population consists of all secondary school headmasters in the district; three female and two male headmasters make up the sample size, which was determined by stratified random sampling. Data collection was carried out using a self-developed semi-structured interview methodology in order to identify the many issues that headmasters of secondary schools encounter. The data collected from the interviews was analyzed using thematic analysis. The results shed light on a range of challenges faced by headmasters of secondary schools, including impediments to the implementation of extracurricular and curriculum activities, insufficient budgetary provisions, restricted resources, political intervention, and estrangement from society. The research emphasizes the necessity of assigning administrative power to subordinate levels, making adequate financial arrangements, and encouraging active community engagement as essential tactics for improving secondary education. Through the implementation of suggested measures and resolution of these issues, policymakers and other relevant parties can promote the development of the educational infrastructure, ultimately improving the standard of secondary education in District Lasbela, Balochistan.

Keywords: School Administration, Issues and challenges, Secondary Schools,

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1. Introduction

Embarking on a journey through the nuanced landscape of secondary education, our study delves into the administrative challenges encountered by secondary school headmasters in District Lasbela. With a lens focused on phenomenology, we unravel the intricacies and hurdles that shape their daily experiences at the helm of educational

institutions (Sain, 2023). This exploration is not merely academic; it unveils critical insights essential for nurturing educational excellence and fostering impactful change within the educational ecosystem. Join us as we illuminate the path toward enhancing secondary education through a deeper understanding of the challenges faced by these educational leaders (Phulpoto, Oad, & Imran, 2024). Education is a fundamental right that must be provided equally and is obligatory, regardless of whether it's in urban or metropolitan areas. It reflects the socio-political awareness within society to cultivate skilled and capable human resources for the nation (Shultz, 1961). O Kumbo (1998) suggests that schools should ensure fair and unbiased delivery of teaching and learning, managed and organized efficiently to attain exceptional educational goals and objectives. Both public and private sectors need to ensure effective and efficient school management practices through collaborative understanding among teams and communities to fulfill overarching educational objectives (Olorisade, 2011). In the national education system, secondary education holds a vital role, serving as a cornerstone for enhancing individuals' skills, behaviors, and overall qualities (Ahmad, Rashid, & Ali, 2023). To effectively achieve educational goals, secondary schools necessitate competent and proficient administrators. Headmasters or principals in public secondary schools encounter various challenges in managing students, teachers, finances, support staff, and issues arising from parental involvement in school affairs. These challenges encompass issues like discipline, unpaid school fees, parental pressure, student dropout rates, staff deficiencies, and budget constraints (Atieno & Simatwa, 2012).

A crucial aspect of education lies in the necessity for effective administration to foster intellectual growth among students and society. It's through proper school administration that the intellectual capacity of both students and society can be developed (Hafeez, Iqbal, & Imran, 2021). The quality of school environments is contingent upon successful learning experiences, irrespective of whether the schools are private or public. An essential element in school administration is the incorporation of activities that hold significance for a dynamic and evolving society (Asadullah et al., 2018).

Efficient school administration translates interests and objectives into achievable outcomes, fostering overall success across various developmental areas. A leader inspires, communicates positively, and guides a team to achieve the well-defined goals and objectives of an educational institution. School leadership plays a critical role in imbuing significance and positive change in both teachers and students, encouraging the creation of an engaging teaching and learning environment within the classroom (Oad & Niazi, 2021). The responsibility of school administration includes planning, organizing, coordinating, and allocating resources and staff personnel in alignment with the school's needs and requirements (such as funds, equipment, and facilities), ensuring systematic maintenance of the school's infrastructure to realize educational goals and objectives (Marshall, 1991). A school administrator serves as the institution's leader, overseeing all school activities and liaising with the district and local education management. They address both indoor and outdoor educational challenges and socioeconomic issues, which significantly impact their performance and pose challenges and obstacles to their execution (Parveen et al., 2021).

Head teachers in secondary schools face various challenges, including inadequate curriculum delivery and assessment methods, limited resources such as teachers, books,

and learning materials, lack of cooperation from both teachers and the community with school administration, and issues related to the quality of education. These challenges hinder the smooth operation of the teaching and learning process in schools (Shah et al., 2023). Headmasters of secondary schools in District Lasbela, Balochistan, face a variety of issues and challenges throughout the year, including interpersonal roles, self-confidence, authority, and power, school document maintenance, and assignment of tasks and roles to teaching and non-teaching staff. Most school administrators are intellectually and logically challenged in their schoolwork, and they are practically untrained and underqualified to meet the demands of innovative school administration. It has a negative impact on the school of administration's overall success and performance. From a role and hierarchical standpoint, the school administrator seat is critical. It is the only authority that assigns equal and meritorious responsibility to all employees. School administrators are frequently confronted with the operation's traditional challenges and issues pertaining to school and education. Hence, this study aims to explore the specific administrative challenges encountered by headmasters in managing school operations at secondary schools in the Lasbela district, as perceived by the headmasters themselves.

2. Literature Review

Secondary school headmasters in District Lasbela face many administrative problems that inhibit secondary education's growth and effectiveness. These educational leaders face logistical and bureaucratic challenges that prevent them from providing effective education (Sain, 2023). Lack of understanding of these difficulties' nature and magnitude hinders efforts to develop focused treatments and remedies. Thus, phenomenological research on secondary school headmasters' administrative challenges in District Lasbela, Balochistan, is necessary. This study seeks to identify, analyze, and explain the root causes to influence policy and strategic actions to improve secondary education (Chachar, Ullah & Ujjan, 2023).

Educational administration involves planning, organizing, coordinating, and controlling efforts within schools to enhance management efficiency and effectiveness, aiming to achieve educational goals and maintain quality (John Dewey, 1916). Leadership plays a pivotal role in academic success, as education is crucial for human development and societal progress (Bush, 2008). Educational management integrates resources to achieve educational objectives, with modern innovations aimed at improving organizational effectiveness (Robbins, 1999). Despite challenges such as resistance and external pressures, the administrator's performance and team efficiency are central to effective school management (Early & Weindling, 2012). Educational leadership involves critical decision-making and coordination of academic activities, fostering cooperation among stakeholders (Cronje & Motlatla, 2004). School administrators execute school objectives, facing criticism and obstacles yet striving to optimize outcomes (Huber, 2004). Leadership inspires teamwork, motivates staff, and engages students in achieving educational goals (Khosro, Oad, & Ahmad, 2023).

Management skills and the ability to optimize resources, formulate policies, implement them decisively, and ensure accountability are essential for effective school administration (Inyang, 2008). School administration plays a primary executive role, addressing various societal constraints such as political autocracy and social tensions. Administrators often face challenges when implementing policies due to stakeholder

obstruction and resource constraints, which impact school operations negatively (Okeke, 2008). Incompetent supervision, inadequate record-keeping, and ineffective teaching strategies contribute to declining educational standards (Belo, 2016). Responsible administration bridges communication gaps between stakeholders, supports teacher development, and fosters effective teamwork (Yarive & Coleman, 2005).

The school administrator holds accountability for managing conflicts, resource allocation, and disciplinary issues while overseeing daily operations (Atif, 2023). Effective leadership and proficient administration are crucial for school success, as administrators make strategic decisions, ensure compliance with government standards, and foster positive relationships with stakeholders (Kochhar, 2011). Administrators act as intermediaries between government policies and educators, transmitting feedback to policymakers and implementing changes as necessary (Okeke, 2008). In addition to managing day-to-day operations and addressing societal issues, administrators must navigate socioeconomic challenges and foster a positive school environment (Belo, 2016). As the central figure in the school, the administrator's leadership determines the school's credibility and success (Grissom et al., 2021).

The school headmaster functions as a leader who is expected to possess the capacity to embody and remain dedicated to the organizational vision and objectives (Blankstein, 2004). Challenges stemming from societal shifts in the new millennium necessitate innovative approaches from school leaders, prompting a departure from conventional methods of problem-solving (Abu-Tineh et al., 2008). The primary issues identified include disparities in general and professional education, ambiguous educational standards, inadequate teaching materials, scarcity of skilled personnel, and poorly managed school curricula (Hashmi, 2000). Furthermore, a lack of political commitment to educational improvement, student enrollment in unsuitable disciplines, insufficient guidance and counseling, parental neglect of children's education, and limited financial resources contribute to the substandard quality of education (Hashmi, 2000). Pakistan's education sector receives the lowest budget allocation in South Asia, falling significantly short of the promised 7% budget allocation by 2015 (Iqbal, 2012). Despite school leaders' efforts to develop compelling visions, insufficient funding hinders their ability to translate these visions into reality (Hashmi, 2000). Consequently, schools face shortages of teachers, who are often underpaid and demotivated, impeding their commitment to education (Shahzadi & Perveen, 2002; Zafar, 2003). This underscores the profound financial challenges confronting school administrators and principals.

The head teacher serves as the primary executor and representative of the school, both internally and externally, responsible for implementing education and curriculum policies and developing plans accordingly (Kochhar, 2011). However, the education system in Pakistan faces severe challenges, particularly in rural areas, where schools lack basic facilities such as infrastructure, sanitation, and water and electricity, significantly impacting teaching and learning activities (Kochhar, 2011). Despite these challenges, the school manager seeks input from teachers and staff, encourages community participation, and fosters team building efforts (Kochhar, 2011). However, research indicates that head teachers face significant challenges in providing quality education, particularly due to a lack

of access to a wide range of textbooks and a shortage of trained and skilled teachers, especially female teachers (Nayar & Salim, 2002; Siddiqui, 2007).

Schools in Balochistan often grapple with resource shortages and ineffective resource utilization, posing significant challenges for school leadership (Asadullah et al., 2018). Inadequate infrastructure leads to overcrowded classrooms, adversely impacting student learning outcomes and attention (Asadullah et al., 2018). Insufficient funding, often subject to cuts, hinders school management's ability to provide necessary infrastructure and facilities for students and teachers (Abdulrasheed & Belo, 2015). Additionally, government authorities pay limited attention to and lack accountability for such schools, resulting in high dropout and absenteeism rates (Abdulrasheed & Belo, 2015). Furthermore, the poor retention rate of teachers can be attributed to their involvement in teachers unions and political affiliations, leading to a disregard for school management and authority (Owate and Okpra, 2013).

The head teacher holds accountability for maintaining school discipline and managing all disciplinary activities, as any disruptions negatively impact the school administration's credibility. When teachers become demotivated and dissatisfied with school administration's behavior and attitude, they may resist directives and even influence others against the head teacher to serve their own interests (Foster, 1989). The challenges intensify when trained and highly professional teachers feel undervalued and underpaid, affecting classroom performance and hindering the head teacher's ability to achieve school objectives (Kingala, 2000). The school's quality performance relies heavily on the exceptional skills and efficiency of the head teacher, who bears responsibility for both its success and failure (Kingala, 2000). Despite school management's efforts to maintain and enhance performance, severe issues and challenges often hinder consistent improvement, impeding the establishment of educational standards and achievement of institutional objectives (Shah et al., 2023).

Assessment stands as a critical pillar for academic sustainability and the attainment of objectives. The development of an assessment plan and procedure should involve consultation with the team, coupled with regular monitoring of students' progress and performance. School administration bears the responsibility to guide and counsel teachers on the utilization of effective tools and techniques for proper student assessment. Rono (2013) highlights that the examination system's ineffectiveness and poor quality hinder its ability to accurately evaluate students' authentic performance.

The education system's fragmentation into different systems based on financial status has led to social problems intertwined with financial aspects. This division results in separate education systems for the wealthy and the poor, posing challenges for principals in maintaining educational standards within their schools (Saeed et al., 2013). Political interference further exacerbates these challenges, particularly concerning teachers' appointments, transfers, and promotions, as educational institutions are often compelled to align with ruling political parties rather than prioritize national development (Saeed et al., 2013). Additionally, institutions are significantly influenced by policy-making at a broader level, as political influence remains prevalent within educational leadership hierarchies. The instability of the political system introduces further hurdles for principals in effectively implementing educational policies (Ghazi et al., 2013).

Headmasters in Pakistani schools in general and in Balochistan particularly often face uncertainty due to frequent transfers, which are often made based on factors other than merit or necessity (Suleman, 2015). These malpractices not only affect the psychological well-being of school principals but also impact students' academic achievement, as head teachers transferred to new schools struggle to adjust to their new environments (Ahmad et al., 2013; Hoy & Weinstein, 2006). Furthermore, such transfers have significant negative effects on the social lives of these school heads, as their families endure uncertainty and instability (Hoy & Weinstein, 2006). This study aims to identify the primary challenges faced by secondary school headmasters, which adversely affect the effectiveness of schools, teaching methods, student performance, and outcomes. While previous research has largely focused on the management roles of secondary school headmasters, their initiatives, and the techniques they employ to address challenges, this study seeks to document the specific problems encountered by secondary school headmasters in Lasbela district, drawing from their firsthand experiences.

3. Research Methodology

This section describes the methodology used in the current study, which focuses on qualitative research in the context of examining secondary school headmasters' viewpoints on administrative difficulties. The nature, extent, and data saturation process of the study problem were considered when choosing the phenomenological design. All headmasters of secondary and higher secondary schools in the district made up the population. Five headmasters three from boys' schools and two from girls' schools were chosen through a stratified random sampling technique. Semi-structured interviews and other data gathering methods were used, and thematic analysis was used to analyze the data.

4. Results and Findings of the study

Five semi-structured interviews were conducted with the headmasters. The analysis of the data reveals that headmasters at the secondary and higher secondary levels in the Lasbela district experience a variety of administrative issues and challenges. According to the headmasters' perspectives, the following issues and challenges emerged as significant.

Complications in implementation of Curricular and Co-Curricular Activities

While co-curricular activities are highly valued for children's overall development, they are viewed as a significant issue, particularly in Balochistan's Lasbela region. Most participants in this study have indicated that several issues impede the implementation of curricular and co-curricular activities at secondary-level schools, including the low socioeconomic background of students, inadequate physical resources, lack of modern technology, insufficient teacher professional training, shortage of textbooks, and inadequate provision of tools and equipment.

One of the participants (Participant 3) highlighted the challenge of implementing curricular activities without textbooks, stating, "we get insufficient quantity of textbooks from the textbook board hence it is a challenge to implement even curricular activities to its potential." While another participant emphasized the impossibility of using co-curricular

activities at the secondary level due to a lack of teacher training and shortage of human resources, stating, "...our teachers who should carry out such activities are not well trained as well as they are employed to the tasks which are not aligned to their portfolio just because of shortage of human resources" (Participant 2).

Inadequate Human Resources

The analysis of the study revealed a shortage of secondary school teachers, as participants emphasized the lack of Secondary School Teachers (SST) in secondary schools. One participant mentioned, "...in my school, Junior Vernacular Teacher (JVT) are teaching 9th and 10th classes due to the absence of secondary school teachers, and SST positions remain unfilled." Another participant (Participant 5) added that "...Additionally, the lack of Secondary School Teachers (SST) has increased the burden of current employees, which has an impact on the standard of instruction given to students."

Inadequate Infrastructure

The analysis of the data uncovered inadequate infrastructure in secondary-level schools. Nearly all participants strongly expressed concerns regarding the lack of proper infrastructure and insufficient allocation of physical resources. Specifically, the study revealed deficiencies in buildings, equipment, libraries, playgrounds, toilets, laboratories, and other physical resources, including shortages of essential items such as whiteboards, markers, and watercolors. Respondents highlighted that due to the lack of buildings and classrooms, classes are overcrowded, making it difficult to effectively monitor large class sizes.

One participant (Participant 3) noted, "...due to shortages of buildings and classrooms, teachers struggle to manage classes effectively, making it challenging to address individual student needs and hindering optimal learning in overcrowded classrooms." While another participant (Participant 4) added that "...the teaching-learning process thrives when appropriate materials are available. However, at our secondary-level schools, there is a severe shortage of materials essential for the teaching-learning process. Consequently, we are unable to conduct classes effectively."

Poor Discipline and Management

Some respondents of the study highlighted disciplinary issues arising from inefficient teamwork, student misconduct, violations, and disruptions during the teaching-learning process. These issues contribute to disciplinary challenges within the school environment. Additionally, respondents pointed out management issues stemming from inadequate support from governments and the lack of skills among school staff, leading to mismanagement problems. Despite these challenges, school headmasters expressed their efforts to address and mitigate such issues.

A male respondent stated, "...students' misconduct contributes to disciplinary issues." Additionally, the same respondent noted, "...low skills and cooperation among the team, as well as inadequate support from governments in distributing materials for organizing and managing school activities, contribute to management issues."

Insufficient Budgetary Allocation

Most study participants identified insufficient budget allocation as a major issue, noting that funds are allocated district-wise and distributed to tehsils. However, participants reported inadequate distribution of funds among schools at tehsil level, highlighting this as a common concern. Insufficient budgetary allocations pose numerous challenges for schools, including the inability to introduce instructional communication technology, smart boards for teaching, and new programs aimed at enhancing the quality of education. Participants emphasized the critical role of adequate financing in addressing these issues and improving the overall quality of education. One headmaster (Participant 2) articulated, "...while the modern world has made significant advancements in quality education, schools in Balochistan, particularly in Lasbela, continue to adhere to traditional patterns due to financial constraints. There is a pressing need for the introduction of well-structured programs and instructional communication technology to improve the quality of education."

Interference by Teachers' Union and Political Entities

Teachers' unions and political support also emerged as significant factors affecting the educational landscape, as highlighted by study participants. The influence of teachers' unions and political backing can impact various aspects of school operations and policies. Participants noted that the involvement of unions and political support can both positively and negatively affect decision-making processes, resource allocation, and the overall functioning of schools. One of the participants (Participant 3) remarked, "...teachers' unions play a crucial role in advocating for the rights and welfare of educators. However, their influence can sometimes create challenges, particularly when it comes to decision-making and school policies." Furthermore, a female participant stated, "...political backing can sometimes lead to positive outcomes for schools, it can also result in inefficiencies or mismanagement if decisions are not made in the best interest of education."

5. Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendation

The study's findings highlight the numerous issues and challenges faced by headmasters. Notably, the implementation of curricular activities is hindered by a dearth of textbooks and changes in curriculum. To address this, teachers require in-service training aligned with curriculum changes to effectively implement new educational frameworks. This finding resonates with prior research by Inyang (2008) and Daniel Katz (2000). Moreover, inadequate infrastructure poses a significant hurdle, as schools lack essential physical resources like textbooks and facilities such as libraries, laboratories, and proper sanitation. The absence of modern technology exacerbates these challenges, making it difficult to execute both curricular and co-curricular activities. This observation aligns with the research of Othman and Abdullah (2012). Additionally, a shortage of Secondary School Teachers (SST) at secondary-level schools further complicates the educational landscape. Disciplinary issues, such as student misconduct and classroom disruptions, also impede the teaching and learning environment. These findings are consistent with existing literature on educational management and student behavior such as Anjum et al. (2012), Shah et al. (2023) and Ahmed et al. (2019) who in their respective studies found results similar to the findings of this research. Furthermore, the study highlights the critical issue of inadequate

budget allocations for schools. Insufficient funding limits the introduction of new activities and programs essential for students' holistic development. Addressing this financial shortfall is imperative for fostering an enriching educational environment.

The study's findings highlight several challenges encountered by headmasters in secondary-level schools. To address these challenges effectively, the following recommendations are proposed:

- Government and the Ministry of Education should prioritize the provision of adequate infrastructure, including classrooms, libraries, laboratories, and playgrounds. Additionally, ensuring access to essential resources such as textbooks is crucial for promoting quality education in schools.
- In-service and pre-service training programs should be made available to teachers, particularly in instances of curriculum changes. Equipping educators with the necessary skills and knowledge will enhance their ability to implement new educational frameworks successfully.
- There is a pressing need for an efficient allocation of an annual budget for schools. Adequate funding will enable the introduction of modern technology and innovative programs aimed at fostering the holistic development of students.
- Government authorities should address the provision of essential physical resources, including access to clean water, proper sanitation facilities, and well-equipped laboratories and libraries. These amenities are fundamental for creating a conducive learning environment for students.
- By implementing these recommendations, stakeholders can work towards overcoming the challenges faced by headmasters in secondary-level schools, ultimately promoting the delivery of quality education and enhancing student outcomes.

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